

An Appreciative Inquiry into the Service Needs of Doctoral Student Hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Dr Mary Joan Camilleri
Head of Counselling Services Unit, Health and Wellness Centre
University of Malta
Judge Paolo Debono Str., Tal-Qroqq, Msida
joan.camilleri@um.edu.mt

Purpose

The Counselling Services Unit adopting research and evidence based interventions regularly refers to studies regarding student wellbeing at the University of Malta to plan its way forward. Quantitative studies conducted by Cefai and Camilleri (2009) and Cuschieri et al (2020) indicated that 65% of the students felt regularly satisfied and confident about their wellbeing. Over 50% of the students reported feeling overwhelmed. Third- and fifth-year students finishing their under-graduate and Master's degree respectively felt more stressed than first-year or single students. Dalli Gonzi and Camilleri (2021) noted that third, and final-year students tended to be in transition with final-year students moving into professional practice. 40% of students surveyed had difficulty discussing problems with anyone, including family and friends while 96% noted that their greatest source of stress were exams and assignments. Cefai and Camilleri (2009), recommended further studies taking on board students' views, particularly the avoidance of professional help due to stigma. This inquiry adopts this recommendation for doctoral students.

The inquiry aims at a) increasing understanding of doctoral students' experiences during their doctorate journey; b) gaining insights into strategies used and resources required by doctoral students to better cope with their studies; c) supporting the emergence of themes that identify ways of facilitating a healthy adjustment/transition through the doctoral journey; d) creating and evaluating relevant interventions.

Design

To attain these aims an appreciative inquiry interview was conducted with volunteering doctoral students (around 20), using thematic analysis. All participants were over 18 years of age, and of any gender. An Appreciative inquiry (Bushe & Kassam, 2005; Cooperrider, Whitney & Stavros, 2008) approach focuses on the participant's internal strengths leading to a positive perspective of change and transition rather than perceiving change as imposed by an external body. In this manner evidence based practices are developed through the development of the strengths of the participants in a democratic manner (De Jaegher & Di Paolo, 2007) creating a positive atmosphere (Waters, & White, 2015)

The Doctoral School, acting as gate-keeper, sent an email invitation in the form of an information and recruitment letter to all doctoral students. Volunteering students were chosen on a first come first served basis and asked to sign a consent form indicating their acceptance to participate. Participants sat for a one-to-one audio recorded interview, to explore the research questions listed above. The interviewer bracketed/suspended their biases, assumptions, theories, or previous experiences during the interviews to see and describe the essence of the specific phenomenon they were researching. Participants could benefit directly from the interview by raising personal awareness of their doctoral process further

understanding how they could be supported. Their participation would support the development of higher quality services for themselves and future students.

Results

Seventeen (17) participants were female and three (3) participants male. Eleven (11) participants were married, with nine (9) having children. Only two (2) participants were unemployed. Participants hailed from various Faculties and their ages ranged 18 - 28 to + 50.

Participants hesitated when replying to the question ‘what is working for you?’ Most started with what worried them, in the habitual problem-solving manner. Participants noted that passion for the subject being researched was essential to retain self-motivation. When the research topic is of personal interest and related to one’s workplace this supports the application of findings to the field, providing immediate feedback on the outcomes. This aspect, while motivating the student, is predominantly applicable for humanistic researches rather than the science ones. Participants reported feeling overwhelmed by feelings such as loneliness and isolation which went beyond those experienced through the COVID-19 mandatory self-quarantine and seclusion due to health reasons. Their narratives were punctuated with ‘you know’ implying the need to be understood and third person singular and plural ‘you/we’ implying distancing from psycho-emotional pain, possibly dissociation from their suffering self (Wheeler, 2003). Many participants noted that when their supervisors were available, well versed and challenging they experienced them as concurrently helpful and anxiety provoking. Less directive supervision worked well with self-directed participants. The supervisor-supervisee relationship is influenced by their personality characteristics which need to be considered for the relationship to be effective. The majority of participants highly appreciated the workshops and symposia organised by the Doctoral School, finding them useful to learn, how to write publishable articles, to review and write abstracts for conferences and research methods. They expressed a wish for more workshops at different times so they would not coincide with their working hours, noting that workshops regarding research methods need to be taught more in-depth differentiating methods required by humanistic researchers from those required by the sciences.

Participants noted how psycho-emotional/financial support from family, friends and partner facilitates their developing a work-life-study balance. Personal financial independence and autonomy as well as working flexibly, allows them to focus more on their doctorate research. Networking with maltese/non-maltese peers interested in the same topic is supportive, speeding knowledge accumulation. Participants insisted that their needs did not reflect the presence of mental ill health or lack of wellbeing but rather a need to work within a community of doctoral students.

Stress is felt due to the doctoral students' ongoing transition from students to experts which influences their circumstances, identity and role (Bridges, 2003). Given the satisfaction obtained from the Doctoral School workshops, participants requested more of them. They were ready to attend training such as time management, stress management and mindfulness practice if these were offered through the Doctoral School.

We would like to thank the Pro Rector for Staff and Student Affairs and the Doctoral School Director for their ongoing support

References

Bridges, W. *Managing Transition*; Da Capo Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2003.

Bushe GR, Kassam AF (2005). When is appreciative inquiry transformational? A meta-analysis. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 41(2), 161-181.

Cefai, C. & Camilleri, L. (2009). *Healthy Students, Health Lives: The Health of Maltese University Students*; European Centre for Educational Resilience and Socio-Emotional Health, University of Malta: Msida, Malta.

Cooperrider DL, Whitney D, Stavros JM (2008). *Appreciative inquiry handbook: For leaders of change* (2nd ed.). San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

Cuschieri, S.; Attard, J.; Bartolo, P.A.; Attard, L.; Cilia, J. & Cacciottolo, J. (2020) *Learning, Teaching and Assessment during the Pandemic at the University of Malta. Findings of the SALT Surveys*; University of Malta: Msida, Malta.

Dalli Gonzi, R. Camilleri, J. (2021). The Role of Appreciative Inquiry to Supporting Students' Healthy Transition into the Post-Graduate World: A Case Study at the University of Malta. *Sustainability*. 13, 5365. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105365>

De Jaegher, H.; Di Paolo, E.A. (2007). Participatory sense-making: An enactive approach to social cognition. *Phenomenol. Cogn. Sci.* 6, 485–507. [[CrossRef](#)]

Waters, L.; White, M. (2015) Case Study of a school wellbeing initiative: Using appreciative inquiry to support positive change. *Int. J. Wellbeing*, 5, 19–32. [[CrossRef](#)]

Wheeler, G. Contact and creativity: The Gestalt cycle in context. (2003) In *Creative License: The Art of Gestalt Therapy*; Spagnuolo-Lobb, M., Amendt-Lyons, N., Eds.; Springer Wien: New York, NY, USA, pp. 163–178.